

Experimental

***N*₁₀-Carboethoxyphenothiazine (1a)**: A mixture of phenothiazine (199 g, 0.1 mol), substituted haloester (10.85 g, 0.1 mol) in dry acetone (40 ml) and anhydrous K₂CO₃ (2 g) was refluxed for 24 h, then cooled, filtered and the solvent removed under reduced pressure. The resulting solid was recrystallised from ethanol to furnish 1a (23.0 g, 85%), m.p. 173° (Found: C, 66.38; H, 4.79; N, 5.14; S, 11.78. C₁₅H₁₂O₂NS calcd. for: C, 66.42; H, 4.79; N, 5.16; S, 11.80%); ν_{\max} 1 710 (C=O ester) and 1 600 cm⁻¹ (C=C); δ 1.3 (3H, t, ester CH₃), 4.2 (2H, q, ester CH₂) and 6.9–7.5 (8H, m, ArH).

***N*₁₀-Hydrazidophenothiazine (2a)**: To a solution of 1a (2.71 g, 0.01 mol) in ethanol (50 ml), hydrazine hydrate (0.5 g, 0.01 mol) was added and the reaction mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 2–3 h, then cooled. The resulting solid was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol to yield 2a (2.18 g, 85%), m.p. 171° (Found: C, 60.60; H, 4.20; N, 16.27. C₁₅H₁₁ON₂S calcd. for: C, 60.70, H, 4.28; N, 16.34%); ν_{\max} 3 350 (NHNH₂) and 1 670 cm⁻¹ (C=O); δ 2.5 (2H, s, NH₂), 7.0–7.5 (8H, m, ArH) and 7.8 (1H, s, CONH).

4-Aryl-1-(*N*₁₀-phenothiazinoyl)thiosemicarbazide (3a): A mixture of 2a (0.257 g, 0.001 mol) and phenyl isothiocyanate (0.135 g, 0.001 mol) was refluxed in alcohol for 3–4 h, then cooled and the solvent removed under reduced pressure. The resulting solid was recrystallised from ethanol to furnish 3a (0.3 g, 75%), m.p. 152° (Found: C, 61.13, H, 4.01; N, 14.12. C₂₀H₁₆ON₂S₂ calcd. for: C, 61.22; H, 4.08; N, 14.28%); ν_{\max} 3 350–3 400 (NH), 1 670 (CONH) and 1 325–1 354 cm⁻¹ (C=S); δ 7.5–7.6 (13H, m, ArH) and 7.8 (1H, s br, NHCO exchangeable with D₂O).

4-Aryl-3-(*N*₁₀-phenothiazinyl)-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (4a): Compound 3a (0.392 g, 0.001 mol) was refluxed with 2*N* NaOH (2 ml) for 3 h, then cooled and filtered. The filtrate on acidification with glacial acetic acid gave a solid which when recrystallised from ethanol gave 4a (0.3 g, 80%), m.p. 74° (Found: C, 64.13; H, 3.69; N, 14.92. C₂₀H₁₄N₄S₂ calcd. for: C, 64.17; H, 3.74; N, 14.97%); ν_{\max} 3 250–3 300 (NH) and 1 600–1 620 cm⁻¹ (C=N); δ 7–7.9 (13H, m, ArH) and 11.5–12.0 (1H, s, SH).

5-Arylamino-2-(*N*₁₀-phenothiazinyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole (5a): To a mixture of 3a (0.392 g, 0.001 mol) in NaOH (4*N*; 4 ml) was added I₂ solution in KI till the colour of I₂ persisted. The reaction mixture was further concentrated for 4–5 h, then cooled and poured into ice-cold water. The resulting solid was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol to give 5a (0.25 g, 70%), m.p. 158° (Found: C, 67.01; H, 3.86; N, 15.59; S, 8.91. C₂₀H₁₄ON₄S calcd. for: C, 67.03; H, 3.91; N, 15.64; S, 8.93%); ν_{\max} 3 150–3 250 (NH), 1 610–1 625 (C=N) and 1 600 cm⁻¹ (C=C); δ 6.7 (1H, s, NH) and 7–8 (13H, m, ArH).

5-Arylamino-2-(*N*₁₀-phenothiazinyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazole (6a): Compound 3a (0.392 g, 0.001 mol) was

dissolved in syrupy phosphoric acid (3 ml), heated at 120° for 50 min kept overnight and then poured into ice-cold water. The resulting solid was filtered and recrystallised to give 6a (0.3 g, 80%), m.p. 59° (Found: C, 64.11, H, 3.71; N, 14.90; S, 17.08. C₂₀H₁₄N₄S₂ calcd. for: C, 64.17; H, 3.74; N, 14.97; S, 17.11%); ν_{\max} 3 200–3 300 (NH), 1 600–1 625 (C=N); 700–720 cm⁻¹ (C–S–C); δ 6.7–6.8 (1H, s, NH) and 7.0–7.8 (13H, m, ArH).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF PHENOTHIAZINE ESTERS (1)^a, HYDRAZIDES (2)^a, THIOSEMICARBAZIDES (3)^a, TRIAZOLES (4)^a, OXADIAZOLES (5)^a AND THIADIAZOLES (6)^a

Compd. no.	Yield %	M.p. °C	Mol. formula
1b	80	205	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂ S
1c	75	159	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ S
1d	75	156	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₂ S
2b	80	189	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ ON ₂ S
2c	85	181	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ ON ₂ S
2d	85	209	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ S
3b	75	70	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ ON ₂ S ₂
3c	70	158	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ ON ₂ S ₂
3d	80	175	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂
4b	85	67	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₄ S ₂
4c	75	160	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₄ S ₂
4d	75	66	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₄ S ₂
5b	75	161	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ ON ₄ S
5c	70	150	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ ON ₄ S
5d	80	155	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₄ S
6b	70	55	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₄ S ₂
6c	70	102	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₄ S ₂
6d	75	70	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₄ S ₂

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Phytochemical Investigation of *Pedilanthus tithymaloides* (L.) Poit.

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[N continuation of our previous works^{1,2} on triterpenoids of *Euphorbiaceae*, the chemical investigation of *Pedilanthus tithymaloides* Poit. (*Euphorbiaceae*)³ was undertaken. *P. tithymaloides* is a

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small shrub growing abundantly in central and eastern provinces of India. A perusal of literature revealed that some works⁴ have been reported on this plant. We now report the results of our systematic screening of the leaves of this plant.

The air-dried powdered leaves of *P. tithymaloides* were successively extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) and benzene. The petroleum ether extract was concentrated and chromatographed over silica gel. Elution of the column with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) afforded a solid, m.p. 88°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3360 cm⁻¹, identified as n-hentriacontanol by the usual comparison (m m.p., co-tlc and co-ir).

Further elution of the column with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) and benzene (1:1) mixture furnished a solid crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°)-methanol (3:1), C₃₀H₅₈O (*M*⁺ 428) m.p. 132–35°, which gave yellow colour with tetranitromethane. Ir spectrum of the compound showed ion bands at ν_{\max} (KBr) 3420 (hydroxyl) and 1640 cm⁻¹ (unsaturation), and formed an amorphous monoacetate C₃₂H₅₆O₂ on acetylation with acetic anhydride and pyridine. The ¹H nmr spectrum (90 MHz; CDCl₃) of the compound recorded peaks at δ 0.75 (15H, s) for five tertiary C-methyls, a doublet at δ 1.15 (3H, d, *J* 6 Hz) for one secondary C-methyl, a singlet at δ 1.65 (6H, s) for a =C(CH₃)₂ and a broad multiplet around δ 5.65 (1H, m) for an olefinic unsaturation, thus indicating it to be a tetracyclic triterpene. The acetyl derivative of the parent compound on catalytic hydrogenation in glacial acetic acid with Adams catalyst afforded dammaranyl acetate⁵, C₃₂H₅₆O₂, m.p. 138–40°, which on hydrolysis with 10% ethanolic KOH furnished a compound, C₃₀H₅₄O (*M*⁺ 430), m.p. 125–26° identified as demmaranol-A⁵ by m m.p., co-tlc and co-ir with the authentic sample, and conclusively establishing thereby that the triterpene is dehydroadammaranol-A, the location of the olefinic unsaturation at C₂₃–C₂₄ being ascertained from the formation of acetone characterised as its dinitrophenylhydrazone during ozonolysis of the acetate of the triterpene. Incidentally it is the first isolation of this triterpene from plant origin.

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Hydrodynamic Determination of Size and Shapes of Near Spherical Macromolecules

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THE equation,

$$V_E = \frac{[(\eta_{rel})^{0.5} - 1]}{C[1.35(\eta_{rel})^{0.5} - 0.1]} \quad (1)$$

was proposed¹ after the rearrangement of Eiler equation^{2,3} for the determination of voluminosities (V_E) of casein micelles in moderately dilute solutions. The η_{rel} and C were relative viscosity and concentration (g ml⁻¹) respectively. Equation (1) was modified in these laboratories⁴ to

$$V_E = \lim_{C \rightarrow 0} \frac{[(\eta_{rel})^{0.5} - 1]}{C[1.35(\eta_{rel})^{0.5} - 0.1]} \quad (2)$$

and the linear plot of

$$\{(\eta_{rel})^{0.5} - 1\} \{C[1.35(\eta_{rel})^{0.5} - 0.1]\}^{-1} \text{ vs } C \quad (3)$$

extrapolated to zero concentration gave the value of voluminosities of salt-soluble mungbean proteins in very dilute solutions.

Simha⁵ equation,

$$[\eta] = \nu V_E \quad (4)$$

where, $[\eta]$ is intrinsic viscosity and ν is Simha shape factor, provides an easy hydrodynamic approach to the determination of molecular parameters of macromolecules, if V_E is known.

In this test study the molecular parameters such as voluminosities, viscosities, Simha shape factors, frictional coefficient ratios of the bovine serum albumin, hemoglobin and egg albumin were hydrodynamically determined and which compared well with the literature values obtained from more sophisticated methods.

Experimental

Pure bovine serum albumin, hemoglobin and egg albumin (Sigma) were used. All reagents used were of A.R. grade. All-glass double-distilled water was used. Present studies were carried out at 40.0 ± 0.1°. All letter representations in different equations express the same quantity.

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